

**Subjugation and Sexual Objectification of Women in Nollywood Films: A Content
Analytical Study**

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Film is a medium of mass communication in the broadcast category which has touched every segment of the society, deals with every subject and has reached every audience in one way or the other (Onabanjo and M'bayo, 2009). It could also be described as a significant medium of communication designed to entertain as well as inform audiences. They also educate, enlighten, inspire, play back history and provide opportunity for social interactions.

Films are an important and popular medium as well as a tool for studying and understanding society. According to Ateya (2012), films provide great insights on how the culture regards and defines itself, how it expresses its problems, limitations and boundaries and how it provides solutions and remedies to the different problems that shape a certain historical moment. Also, films try to assert certain norms and values and, sometimes, they also try to question others. It was in view of that assertion that Ekwenchi and Adum (2012) note that any credible account of a film industry such as Nigeria's *Nollywood* must first start with the conceptualisation of the industry's output as both local and global culture.

Nigeria has a vibrant film industry. The Nigerian film industry is called Nollywood, coined after Hollywood and Bollywood. By definition, Nollywood is Nigeria's movie industry by Nigerian production teams for the Nigerian people (Opeyemi, 2008). The London *Independent* (May 15, 2010) reports that Nollywood is the second largest film industry in the world in terms of number of annual film productions, placing it ahead of the United States and behind only India.

Since the early 1990s, the Nollywood movie industry has churned out thousands of titles and has successfully brought to limelight many talented Nigerian actors and actresses. There are recurring themes in Nollywood films. Some of those themes have been subject of stern criticisms against the industry. Ogunleye (2003) states that one of the major criticisms of this industry is its thematic obsession with the occult world (juju, black magic, sorcery, ritual murder, witchcraft, etc.), obscenity, prostitution, and 'money worship.' These films, along with their Ghana counterparts, have been described as a mixture of 'horror, magic and melodrama' (p. 12).

Opeyemi (2008) asserts that over the years, the industry has promoted certain identities and images which critics have frowned at. Among these are the image of a ritualistic society, the image of a violent society, the poor portrayal of certain sub-groups and a display of a highly ostentatious and an oligarchic society. These films project imageries and ideas that have to a great extent become a norm, because profiteering has replaced art.

The way Nollywood films and the mass media in general have portrayed women has also been a source of concern to Nigerian women and feminists. There are concerns of subjugation and objectification of the female gender in films and the mainstream media. According to SAGE Publications (21 August, 2014), to sexually objectify a woman is to focus on her body in terms of how it can provide sexual pleasure rather than viewing her as a complete human being with thoughts and feelings. Sexual objectification is the objectification of persons generally based on their sexual attributes. Women are far more likely than men to be objectified and judged by a perceived sexual attractiveness rather than values such as intellectual ability (Dawn, 2011).

Subjugation has to do with one group of people or gender (as is the case in this study) dominating another group or gender by taking away their freedom. It is a situation of placing one gender over another. Subjugation is otherwise called subordination. There are serious concerns of portrayal of subjugation of women in the media. Okunna (2002) notes that in male-dominated societies, women's subordination and men's dominance are so pronounced that their subcultures are literally separated by a world of difference.

A growing number of Nigerian women and feminists have in the past expressed reservations about the portrayal of women in Nigerian video films (Okunna, 1996; Ezeigbo, 1996; Okunna, 2000; Ogunleye, 2003; Azeez, 2008; etc). Various analyses of Nigerian films have mostly concluded that Nigerian films portray and position Nigerian women stereotypically and negatively. Okunna (2000, p. 24), for instance, concludes that Nollywood films are "facilitating the internalisation of the negative images of women by the large audience of local home video films." In line with a feminist ideological perspective, the films were also alleged to position women at the bottom of the power hierarchy in a way that reinforces their domination, suppression and objectification.

Twenty two years have passed since the recorded 'kick-off' of the film industry in 1992. Within that span, hundreds of thousands of films have been produced. According to the National

Film and Video Censors Board, the number of films produced yearly in Nigeria is estimated at between 500 and 1000. By that estimation, there are approximately, 22000 films produced by Nollywood since 1992. Among them, there are films that have females in leading and supporting roles, the consequences of which is that they have the potential to shape audience perceptions about women. Some of those films are *Living in Bondage*, *Glamour Girls*, *Christ in Me*, *Sakobi*, *Domitilla*, *Ije*, *Ukwa*, *What Women Want*, *Abuja Connection*, *Yellow Cassava*, *Game*, *In the Cupboard*, *Half of a Yellow Sun*, *Inale*, among others. There is a continuing search for empirical evidence to support or disprove reservations about the portrayal of women in such Nigerian video films as suppressed and objectified. This study revisits the portrayal of objectification and subjugation of women in Nollywood films, from the turn of the 21st Century to this day.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Numerous studies were conducted on the portrayal of women in Nigerian films in the early years of Nollywood (1992-2000), and it was concluded that Nollywood films did not only limit representations of women to passive and subordinate housewives, but also portrayed them as evil people, who are wicked, vindictive and unfaithful, wayward and of low morality, easily lured by material things, subservient to men, fit for domestic rather than professional and career roles, lazy and dependent on men, sex objects or weaker vessels, etc. (Ezeigbo, 1996; Okunna, 1996; Okunna, 2000; Ogunleye, 2003; Azeez, 2008).

The misrepresentation of the image of women in films even seems to be a global concern as researchers outside Nigeria have also been worried that women tend to be objectified and negatively portrayed in movies (Davis, 2003; Ahlstrand, 2007; Ateya, 2012). As the twentieth century ended, as Okunna (2000) observes, research evidence shows that Nigerian home video films were filled with negative and stereotyped images of women.

In the said first decade of Nollywood, Alao (2011) states that the industry was a male dominated one. Therefore, the men set the agenda and framed the images. However, times have changed. The 21st Century has been marked by various landmarks in Nollywood, not only in better quality of technical aspects of production, better quality of scripting, bigger budgets, international collaborations, richer story lines and more global audience, but also in greater

involvement of women in the nation's movie industry, particularly in the appointment of a woman as the DG of the NFVCB (Ms Patricia Bala), increase in the number of female directors and producers; a lot of women in the industry have moved from just being actresses into the more technical areas of scripting, videography, directing and production among other things.

With these greater involvement of women in Nollywood and other milestones, has the portrayal of women changed in films produced in the 21st Century; and if so, how has the portrayal of subjugation and objectification of women changed over the years against the benchmarks of previous studies?

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the extent of subjugation of women in select Nollywood films (2000-2014).
2. Determine the extent of objectification of women in select Nollywood films (2000-2014).
3. Examine the older and more recent movies and find out if there is a change in the treatment of women in Nollywood films in the 21st Century.
4. Evaluate the older and more recent movies and find out if there is a change in the objectification of women in Nollywood films in the 21st Century.
5. Investigate whether Nollywood films produced by women have less portrayal of subjugation and objectification of women.

1.4 Research Questions

The researcher is guided by the following questions:

1. To what extent are women subjugated in the select Nollywood films?
2. To what extent are women objectified in the select Nollywood films?
3. To what extent has the subjugation of women in Nollywood films changed over the years?

4. To what extent has the objectification of women in Nollywood films changed over the years?
5. Do Nollywood films produced by women have less subjugation and objectification of women than those produced by men?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following are the hypotheses:

1. There is a significant difference in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films between 2000 and 2014.
2. There is a significant difference in the objectification of women in Nollywood films between 2000 and 2014.
3. There is a significant relationship between gender of producers and the extent of subjugation and objectification of women in Nollywood films.

1.6 Scope of the Study

This is a content analysis of the portrayal of women in select Nollywood films produced between 2000 and 2014 with a view to revisiting the objectification and subjugation of women. This specific period was chosen as this was when women began to take part in the technical aspects of film production in an industry that was hitherto thought to be a male-dominated one.

What it means it that the springboards for this study are empirical findings from related studies that were done in the past. The findings of this study were measured against the findings of the previous studies that were done on films produced between 1992 and 2000 to gauge their correlation and observe any change in portrayal. This makes the study a longitudinal one, as it compares trends in portrayal of women in Nollywood films over a period of time

Not all Nollywood films produced between 2000 and 2014 are of interest in this study, rather those Nollywood films that have females in their leading and supporting roles. It is the understanding of the researcher that the same way that selection and placement of stories can help to set agenda in the traditional media, so can the role played by actors determine their

perception by the audience. More prominent roles are assumed to set more agenda for how an actress is perceived. Only films which record is found in the website of the Nigerian Film and Video Censors Board were selected to ensure that they are registered films.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study may be of immense use to the following persons and organisations:

Various players in Nollywood may understand how to project a fair and balanced image of men and women, and become aware of their role in facilitating gender equity or, at least, tolerance.

Nollywood may by the findings of this study assess the place of gender representation as a thematic obsession in the industry. Often times, the producers are not aware of the fact that they are blowing certain gender representations out of proportion. They only care about the storyline. Studies of this nature may make them become aware of it.

The attention of the National Films and Video Censors Board (NFVCB) may be drawn to the extent of women portrayals in the films, and if they are portrayed in an uncomfortable proportion, NFVCB might consider including gender portrayal as a rating category, aside from Violence, Nudity and Strong Language. Feminists and researchers may use the findings of this study for policy decisions and as a resource for future studies respectively.

1.8 Limitations of the Study

This study was not without glitches, the prominent of which was the problem of sampling: there were some difficulties in locating a database of all Nigerian films produced since 2000; as well as getting those films to watch them and code them. The researcher got around this limitation by changing some of the films selected and subscribing to the Internet platform *IrokoTV* for online streaming of the films.

There was a constraint with the design used in the study. While content analysis was appropriate to examine objectively the portrayal of women in the selected Nollywood films, it did not give room to gauge the open-ended opinions of a representative sample of women. It would have been important to do so, because what the researcher considered as subjugation and

objectification might not be seen as such by the women. The researcher tried to get around the limitation by interviewing a few women to get their views on whether women were subjugated and objectified in Nollywood films.

Moreover, there seemed to be a gender consciousness and bias among the interviewees in the in-depth interview session. Most female interviewees decried the extent of female objectification in Nigerian films, while most of the men thought otherwise. However most of those sentimental responses were carefully handled in the further analysis.

1.9 Operationalisation of Concepts

Nollywood Films: Feature length films produced by Nigerians between 2000 and 2014.

Objectification: Explicit and implied emphasis on sensuality and sensual appeal of female actors in the feature length films.

Portrayal: Extent and manner of representations of female actors in the feature length films.

Subjugation: Representations of undue submission, low-esteem, subordination and dependence on the male actors, and sometimes on another female actor.

Women: The female actors in the feature length films who played leading or supporting roles.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter reviews existing knowledge about concepts in the thesis, explores the theoretical frameworks that support this study and also reviews empirical studies related to the work. The essence is to help in any way to illuminate the problem in hand (Edeani, 1995), provide “empirical-cum-theoretical insight into the study in view” (Nwodu, 2006, p. 219) and put the study in perspective. Materials sourced for the reviews are refereed books, journals, monographs, websites, thesis and dissertations.

2.1 Conceptual Review

In this section, the researcher reviews some of the relevant concepts in the thesis and brings to light some of the views of the various authors regarding them.

2.1.1 Nollywood Films: An Overview

The word Nollywood is the generic name for the Nigerian film industry. It was coined following the style of Hollywood (the American film industry) and Bollywood (the Indian film Industry). According to Okome (2007), it is a designation that points to its similarities with Hollywood. Opeyemi (2008) states that by definition, Nollywood is Nigeria's movie industry by Nigerian production teams for the Nigerian people.

Talking about the strides of the film industry in Nigeria, Liston (10 April 2014) reports that Nollywood is Africa's largest movie industry in terms of value and the number of movies produced per year and *The London Independent* (May 15, 2010) ascribes Nollywood as the second largest film industry in the world in number of annual film productions, placing it ahead of the United States and behind only India.

Nollywood films are produced mostly in English language. They are also produced in Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa languages as well as in some of the minority languages such as Ijaw, Efik, Itsekiri, etc. But, according to Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012), the use of the English Language as the main communication tool and the marketing strategies has facilitated the expansion of Nollywood films beyond the shores of the African continent. Nollywood has over the years become a world phenomenon, as its movies are being sold in Ghana, Togo, Kenya,

Uganda and South Africa as well as Jamaica, USA and the UK to name a few. The popularity of Nigerian films now stretches far beyond the country's borders.

Since the early 1990s, the Nollywood movie industry has churned out thousands of titles and has successfully brought to limelight many talented Nigerian actors and actresses. According to the website of the Nigerian Films Video and Censors Board (retrieved 12-12-2014) some 300 producers churn out movies at an astonishing rate—somewhere between 500 and 1,000 a year. Talking about the major themes of Nollywood films, Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012, p. 22) stress that “through an amalgam of Nigerian narrative techniques (African storylines) and Western technology, the industry documents and re-creates sociopolitical and cultural events that occurred within and beyond the country borders.” Many Nollywood movies have themes that deal with the moral dilemmas facing modern Africans. Some movies promote the Christian or Islamic faiths, and some movies are overtly evangelical.

Similarly, Kunzler (2007, p. 1) explains that Nollywood is an industry that “developed out of a context related to domestic and international cultural, economic, and political environments.” It is heterogeneous in nature and can roughly be divided into Yoruba, Hausa and Igbo video films which designate their production centers in the South-West, North and South-East of Nigeria respectively.

Nigeria’s Nollywood is counted among the major business centres of film making in the world. Alamu (2010) remarks that Nigeria’s Nollywood has been viewed as cultural products of the Nation, and the global attention currently enjoyed by it is due to efforts by producers to create a distinct film tradition. The industry has advanced by virtue of the individual efforts of dominant producers and marketers in spite of its burgeoning challenges such as the problems of unabated piracy and the indifference of the government which has denied it the status of a foreign exchange. The industry has also provided employment for the teeming Nigerian population especially the youth.

Even though, the filmmakers make films essentially to make money, Akomfrah (2006, p. 282) argues that they are systematically being ‘guided by the tenets of African nationalism and cultural identity which help them address local concerns.’ Ogunleye (2003, p. 6) states that one of the major criticisms of this new industry is its thematic obsession with the occult world (juju, black magic, sorcery, ritual murder, witchcraft, etc.), obscenity, prostitution, and "money

worship." Nigerian video films, along with their Ghana counterparts, have been described as a mixture of "horror, magic and melodrama"

Ejinkoye (2009) highlights some of the challenges faced by Nollywood. First, the editing is poor. Then, techniques used to signal a transition from one location to another, such as the dissolve and superimposition, are blatantly abused, and the timing of the shots is wrong. The Nigerian industry lacks basic lighting equipment, and in many video films, very high or very low lighting affects the quality of the color. With no deliberate attempt to create a dramatic effect, a good number of the films contain shadows that could have been eliminated with proper lighting.

In all these, it is important to conclude that Nollywood has grown in leaps and bounds over the years. It however has been criticized in terms of the techniques, prevalent themes and certain portrayals.

2.1.2 History and Development of Nollywood Films

There are so many versions of the history of the film industry in Nigeria. Beginning from the origin of the name, Nollywood; even though the name, Nollywood, has an uncertain origin and was derived from acronyms such as Hollywood and Bollywood, Haynes (2005) highlights that it apparently appeared for the first time in print in an article by Matt Steinglass in New York Times in 2002. Nollywood, according to Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012), grew from the rich traditional culture of Nigeria into a supposedly modern internationally recognized industry. Prior to the emergence of Nollywood in the early nineties, theatre and television stations were primarily the medium used by a lot of theatre artists.

Ekwuazi (1984) recounts that the Nigeria's first contact with cinema was in 1903, at the instance of Herbert Macaulay, a foremost nationalist who invited the Balboa and Company who was then doing an exhibition tour of silent films on the West African Coast to Nigeria. The films were shown at the Glover Memorial Hall, Lagos in August, 1903. The success of the Balboa venture paved the way for an influx of European film exhibitors to Nigeria. Itam (2000) notes that shortly after the exhibition tour of the Balboa venture, the colonial government took interest and brought in a lot of films. Similarly, Uchegbu (1992) states that the Nigerian audiences' first experience in film screening was in 1903 at the Glover Memorial Hall. Ekwuazi (1987) narrates

that film was introduced in by a European merchant; but it took the combined efforts of the colonial administration and the church to sustain the industry.

According to Uwah (2011), there were a group of Nigerian filmmakers who carried out film production practice by themselves without Government sponsorship between 1960s and 1980s and due to the high cost of production had to give it up. For many years then, Nigeria remained without film productions and people resorted to stage dramas. Some of those filmmakers included Ola Balogun, Hebert Ogungbe, Eddie Ugboma, Eddie Ugbomah, Ladi Ladebo, Ola Balogun, U.S.A Galadima Wole Soyinka among others. However, with the oil boom, some of these individuals became involved again in the production of indigenous films. By 1970, the first indigenous feature film was produced in Nigeria: Kongi's Harvest. It was however directed by an American and it featured many foreigners as crew members.

According to Onabanjo and M'bayo (2009), the popular view is that the Nigerian movie industry actually started with the 1992 production of 'Living in bondage' by Ken Nebue but the debate on whether a film industry exists in Nigeria or not, had already been going on. Today, video film production is a multi-billion naira industry which provides a source of livelihood for many people both at home and abroad. The industry has also produced many "stars" as well as its own international events.

Reporting the massive growth of the industry in the recent past, The London Independent (May 15, 2010) reports that Nollywood, grew quickly in the 1990s and 2000s and became the second largest film industry in the world in number of annual film productions, placing it ahead of the United States and behind only India. Brown (2013) also reports that in 2013, it was rated as the third most valuable film industry in the world after generating a total revenue of 1.72 trillion naira (US\$10 billion) in 2013 alone, placing it behind India and the United States.

Liston (10 April 2014) reports that the Nigerian film industry is worth 853.9 billion naira (US\$5.1 billion) as at 2014 and produces hundreds of home videos and films per annum. Nigerian cinema is Africa's largest movie industry in terms of value and the number of movies produced per year. Although Nigerian films have been produced since the 1960s, the rise of affordable digital filming and editing technologies has stimulated the country's film and video industry.

Essentially it can also be argued that fundamental factors that gave inspiration to the rise of Nollywood are: 'citizen journalism'. This refers to the individual zeal of some Nigerians to empower themselves in order to make their voices heard by the general public (Okome, 2007). The success of this industry also comes from what Nwachukwu (2003) identifies as the drive for 'commercial viability' This is because while the new video film industry places a high premium on entertainment, it also seeks the pleasure of viewers in order to recoup expenses from their sales by encoding what audiences desire to see.

Nollywood's historical emergence according to Adesokan (2006) hinges on the neoliberal deregulations of many economies in Africa that brought changes in the use of technology, especially of the digital kind, which is open to reformatting in quite imaginative ways.

2.1.3 Objectification of Women

Objectification means treating a person as a thing. *Stanford Encyclopedia* (2010) explains that objectification is a notion central to feminist theory. It can be roughly defined as the seeing and/or treating a person, usually a woman, as an object. Objectification is a term to describe seeing human beings as objects. Representations show people, not as individuals, but as things to be owned, sold, used, etc. The focus here is primarily on sexual objectification, objectification occurring in the sexual realm. Objectification, for Kant (1797) cited in McGregor (1996), involves the lowering of a person, a being with humanity, to the status of an object. In the light of objectification, Kant often speaks about 'degradation', 'subordination', and 'dishonouring' of humanity.

According to SAGE Publications (21 August, 2014), to sexually objectify a woman is to focus on her body in terms of how it can provide sexual pleasure rather than viewing her as a complete human being with thoughts and feelings. Sexual objectification is the objectification of persons generally based on their sexual attributes. Women are far more likely than men to be objectified and judged by a perceived sexual attractiveness rather than values such as intellectual ability (Dawn, 2011). Sexual objectification of women is found in media, in advertising, and not surprisingly, even in news.

Objectification of women means the suggestion that women's value is tied to their looks and sexual appeal to men. When it concerns the reduction of women to physical objects of sexual

desire, it is known as sexual objectification. This is also expressed by the dismemberment of women in the media (Kilbourne, 2002). A sexualised message of women is a typical example of objectification. Female objectification was once thought imponderable but, through a growing body of research, this belief has been proven wrong. The existence and the implications of female objectification have been explored.

Nussbaum (1995) has identified seven features that are involved in the idea of treating a person as an object. That is to say, a person might be objectified if one or a selection of the following properties is adhered to:

1. *Instrumentality*: the treatment of a person as a tool for the objectifier's purposes;
2. *Denial of autonomy*: the treatment of a person as lacking in autonomy and self-determination;
3. *Inertness*: the treatment of a person as lacking in agency, and perhaps also in activity;
4. *Fungibility*: the treatment of a person as interchangeable with other objects;
5. *Violability*: the treatment of a person as lacking in boundary-integrity;
6. *Ownership*: the treatment of a person as something that is owned by another (can be bought or sold);
7. *Denial of subjectivity*: the treatment of a person as something whose experiences and feelings (if any) need not be taken into account.

Langton (2009) has added three more features of objectification as:

1. *Reduction to body*: the treatment of a person as identified with their body, or body parts;
2. *Reduction to appearance*: the treatment of a person primarily in terms of how they look, or how they appear to the senses;
3. *Silencing*: the treatment of a person as if they are silent, lacking the capacity to speak.

Even though men are sometimes objectified, empirical studies have indicated that women are overwhelmingly targeted more for sexually objectifying treatment than men (Fredrickson and Roberts, 1997). The most prominent means of transporting this sexualized female identity is through the mass media.

Saul (2003) explains that some feminist thinkers that women in our society are more identified and associated with their bodies than are men, and, to a greater extent than men, they are valued for how they look. In order to gain social acceptability, women are under constant pressure to correct their bodies and appearance more generally, and make them conform to the ideals of feminine appearance of their time, the so-called 'norms of feminine appearance' (the standards of appearance women feel they should be living up to).

Extensive research has demonstrated the negative results of female objectification in the media. The objectification of women, have serious repercussions including, but not limited to, body shame, appearance anxiety, depression, sexual dysfunction, and eating disorders. Fareed (2012), the status of women in our society, especially in the cultural industry such as the media, has been very sympathetic since ages; they have never given the importance they deserved. Our male chauvinistic society has always been eager to use women but never ready to give them the high pedestal that they justify. Since the old ages women are defined as a commodity or an instrument of luxury.

2.1.4 Subjugation of women

Subjugation is like oppression or conquest: one group takes control over another and forces them to do as they are told. It is a state of being under control or secondary. Vocabulary.com (retrieved 10-11-2014) explains that subjugation is one of many types of injustice in the world. It has to do with one group of people dominating another group by taking away their freedom. It has its Latin root as *subjugat*, which means 'brought under a yoke.' Silima (2013) explains that a subjugated individual means a lower-ranking or an inferior individual. Subjugation is otherwise called subordination.

Regarding subjugation of women, Okunna (2002) notes that in male-dominated societies, women's subordination and men's dominance are so pronounced that their subcultures are literally separated by a world of difference. One such society, she says, is Nigeria. The Nigerian woman is also characterized by low self-esteem because the society has continued to regard her as unimportant and inferior to her male counterpart.

Rodriguez (2007) asserts that women in most settled societies of the world and virtually all class societies have experienced low status, exploitation, oppression, and loss of self-

determination. For example, most settled and class societies transmit names and property through the male line. Given the importance of paternity in patrilineal societies, it is scarcely surprising that many settled and class societies insist on female premarital chastity. The inherent uncertainty of paternity has often produced bizarre and barbarous attempts to secure the fidelity of married women as well.

Wollstonecraft (2009) describes women subjugation as a situation where women are, in common with men, rendered weak and luxurious by the relaxing pleasures which wealth procures; but added to this they are made slaves to their persons, and must render them alluring that man may lend them his reason to guide their tottering steps aright.

Ikokwu (2002) draws attention not only to the gross discrimination against women under this legal system but also to the incongruity of such a system operating in a democratic society in the twenty-first century. Women are equally economically disadvantaged and impoverished in terms of ownership of the means of production such as land. Talking about the subjugation of women in Nigerian society, Ojiakor (1997) in Okunna (2002, p. 3) effectively captures the master-servant relationship between the sexes when she says, “the Nigerian men have always believed that Nigeria belongs to them and women are at best the rent-paying tenants. Over the centuries, women have struggled to say no to this misconception.”

Speaking also about gender relations in Nigeria with relation to subjugation of women, Okunna (2002) understands that gender relations in Nigeria are characterized by a lot of imbalance, to the disadvantage of women. This is the twenty-first century, yet tradition, culture, religion and other factors have continued to widen the disparity between Nigerian men and women, by keeping women in a subordinate position to men. The larger society and the male subculture still see women and their aspirations as subordinate, resulting in a situation in which the marginalisation, trivialisation and stereotyping of women are glaring aspects of Nigerian life.

Ojiakor (1997) effectively captures the master-servant relationship between the sexes when she states, “the Nigerian men have always believed that Nigeria belongs to them and women are at best the rent-paying tenants. Over the centuries, women have struggled to say no to this misconception.” This statement aptly explains subjugation of women.

Subjugation also manifests in economic disempowerment of women, Okoye (2000) shows how, in comparison to men, women are worse hit as a result of their very limited

involvement in economic activities in relation to their male counterparts. Abati (1996) notes that based on concerted research the conclusion has long been reached that women are a de-centred, de-natured sub-species of humanity; harassed by culture, intimidated by politics and subsumed in helplessly patrilineal and patriarchal structures which pamper the male ego.

Okunna (1996) emphasises that the continuous call for women empowerment presupposes the existence of weakness and subjugation. It has become incontrovertible and thoroughly documented that in gender relations; women occupy an inferior position all over the world. The Nigerian woman is also characterized by low self-esteem because the society has continued to regard her as unimportant and inferior to her male counterpart. Right from the beginning of life, society prefers the boy child to the girl child. All through her growing-up years, the girl child is socialized to accept her subordinate position

2.1.5 Gender Portrayal and Stereotypes in the Media

Many studies have been aimed at exploring the way men and women are portrayed in the media. Most of those studies point to a conclusion that women are described as sexual objects and passive participant, while positive characteristics of male are over-implied. What exactly is stereotyping, what does it involve and how does it functions? Stereotyping is a form of representation but a stereotypical representation will often be negative, inaccurate, limited and partial. A stereotype is a distorted, exaggerated or misleading representation of a person or group of people through the reduction of that person or group to a few essential characteristics (Hall, 2007). Stereotypes basically represent a set of ideas or a set of beliefs about people – an ideology – rather than people as they are.

According to Wood (2000) there are four perennial themes of gender portrayal in the media. These themes demonstrate how media reflect and promote traditional arrangements between the sexes.

1. Women are caregivers and men are providers;
2. Men are the competent authorities who save women from their incompetence;

3. Women as subject to men's sexual desires: women as victims and sex objects/men as aggressors; and
4. Women's dependence and men's independence.

Itzin (1986, p. 128) notes that stereotypes are, "deliberately misleading; they perform the function of creating attitudes which, by their very nature, are negative attitudes." They function as a form of propaganda; they are the language of ideology – the way it is communicated.' Espinosa (2010) states that gender roles are prevalent in media, often portraying women as nurturing, gentle, cooperative, concerned with appearance, and sensitive to others; while men are viewed as logical, competitive, independent, assertive, financial providers, skilled in business. Women in media tend to be represented more negatively than men (Rouner, 2003). While men are perceived as hard workers, amusing directive, and physically aggressive (Aubrey and Harrison, 2004), women are displayed as likeable, warm, submissive, passive, and weak (Dill and Thill, 2007).

Women are also more likely than men to display empathic behaviors such as affection, sharing, giving, and concern for others (Glascock, 2001). Women are likely to be portrayed as sex objects in media (Morris, 2006). According to Fareed (2012), the status of women in our society, especially in the cultural industry such as the media, has been very sympathetic since ages; they have never given the importance they deserved. Our male chauvinistic society has always been eager to use women but never ready to give them the high pedestal that they justify. Since the old ages women are defined as a commodity or an instrument of luxury. Sim and Suying (2001) state that the roles assigned to women in the media were most likely to be depicted as non-occupational, and that women are very often shown as being preoccupied with their personal appearance.

Talking about the social impact of media portrayal of gender, Lester and Ross (2003) and Gorham (2004) believe that stereotypes have the potential to produce hatred, violence, and misunderstanding. If we consider the number of media messages that are transmitted and consumed each day coupled with the assertion that media stereotypes actually reinforce and amplify personal stereotypes, there is certainly a huge probability that particularly harmful

effects will ensue. In this way, the media can be said to exacerbate the problem of prejudice and discrimination.

Concerning the portrayal of sex roles, Carter and Steiner (2004) note that past studies have found that the depiction of sex roles in the media have been incredibly narrow, with women often only being shown within the domestic private sphere, but with men being portrayed in a whole variety of different occupations within the public sphere.

2.2 Empirical Review

Previous studies have successfully examined gender roles in many popular forms of media. Those studies are quite extensive and cover many different forms of media, for example: prime-time television, movies, cartoons, music, games and much more recently the internet where new forms of media are being produced (Okunna, 2002; Ottoson and Cheng, 2012).

This section reviews some previous studies that were conducted on the portrayal of women either in Nollywood films or other film industry. The essence is to show that this work, like every research work, is built from previous studies; it also highlights the lacuna that the researcher intends to fill in this study.

2.2.1 Azeez, A. L. (2010) Audience perception of portrayals of women in Nigerian home video films. *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 2(9): 200-207. Online at <http://www.academicjournals.org/jmcs>. Accessed 21-01-2015

This study investigated how Nigerians, particularly women, interpreted the meanings of the representations of women in Nigerian films. It aimed at understanding how Nigerian audience interpreted the meanings of the images of women in Nigerian films, with a focus on investigating whether or not there was a marked difference in the ways different individuals and groups interpreted the representations. The general objectives of this study were to investigate how the Nigerian audience receive and interpret the images of women in Nigerian films; investigate whether or not there is any difference in the ways different individual audience interpret the representations of women in Nigerian films; and to determine factors that influence how the audience interpret the meanings in the representations of women in Nigerian films.

To achieve the objectives of this study, three sessions of focus group discussions involving a representative sample of viewers of Nigerian video films, from different socio-

economic groups were undertaken. The participants ranged according to age, sex, ethnicity and educational level.

Thus, the participants in the first group (26 - 34 years), in the first session, were postgraduate students studying at “masters’ level” on a part time basis at the University of Lagos. The second group (18 – 25 years), and second session, consisted of participants who were in the third and fourth year of their first degree also at the University of Lagos. The participants in the third group (35 to 45 years), and third session, were predominantly less educated people including artisans, market women, shop owners and lower-cadre civil servants. The highest level of education among this group was primary school, which is equivalent to ‘standard six’ in the Nigerian system and which means they were not only predominantly illiterate, but were less exposed than the first two groups.

The participants in the first and second groups were selected through systematic and cluster random sampling techniques respectively. The aim of using these techniques was not to achieve statistical representation, but was rather meant to ensure that diversity was inherent in the composition of the groups. The participants in the third group were selected through a non-probability sampling technique (purposively) from markets and streets in Ibadan, Oyo State in the South-western part of Nigeria.

The study found that there is a marked difference in the ways women and men interpret the meanings embedded in the representations of women in Nigerian films. While men and less educated women interpret the representations in conformist manner, having the preferred meanings of the ideological meanings embedded in the representation, educated women interpret the representations ‘oppositionally’ and ‘agitatively’. It also concluded that there is a marked difference in the ways women, with high education and those with little or no education, perceive the representations of women in Nigerian films. The difference is related to the way each group of women understands and identifies or dis-identifies with the meanings of the images of the films. On this basis, this study proposed a new model for understanding how women in Nigeria interpret popular culture.

Just as the current study, the representations of women in Nigerian films were subjects of the enquiry. The survey design was used in the reviewed study, whereas content analysis was used in the current study.

2.2.2 Okunna, C. S. (1996). Portrayal of women in Nigerian home video films: Empowerment or subjugation? *Africa Media Review*, 10(3): 12-29

Using Igbo language video films as a case in point, the study examined the portrayal of women in films, and the reactions of young women towards this portrayal. The major purpose of which was to gain an insight into what Okunna (1996) considered an apparently novel and unexplored situation at that time: to examine the portrayal of women in the media through their portrayal in selected Igbo language films.

To generate the data for this, data were gathered from a focus group discussion and the class discussion among mass communication undergraduates who were enrolled in a course of critical writing and reviewing. Although the 32-member class comprised male and female students, 26 of them were involved in the discussion of these films. The discussion yielded relevant data for the study. Given the purposeful decision which informed the use of these two categories of respondents, the method of their selection was definitely convenience sampling.

The rationale for the study was that the explosion in the number of local video films was truly astounding. The proliferation and the popularity of these films heightened fears that the little gain that might have been made in this struggle is being eroded by the internalization of the negative images of women by the large audience of local home video films. In addition, a growing number of Nigerian women expressed misgivings about the portrayal of women in Nigerian video films. This study therefore searched for empirical evidence to support or disprove such misgivings. The theory that was used to anchor the study is the 'cultivation theory', based on Gerbner's 'cultivation hypothesis.'

Ten Igbo language video films were used for the study. Questions for the focus group discussion and the class discussion revolved around the following aspects of the films:

- i. The portrayal of women in the films - realistic or otherwise;
- ii. The image of women, *vis-a-vis* the major female characters - negative or positive; and
- iii. Possible influence of this image on the respondents' perception of women.

The image of women in these films was found to be very bad and capable of negatively influencing the perception of women among the large audience of video films in Nigeria. The results of the study indicated that the portrayal of women in Igbo language video films is

unrealistic. The paper concludes that, in this era of concern for women's empowerment, these films are counterproductive and damaging to the cause of women. Rather than contribute to the much-needed empowerment of Nigerian women, such films will only lead to the subjugation of women because they can increase men's disdain for women, sow distrust between women, undermine their confidence in themselves and strengthen the forces which push women to the background in this patriarchal society.

It is advocated that women actors should reject roles that relegate them to second fiddle. The domination of male producers in the home video industry is decried, and women are encouraged to seek more positive and active roles.

The reviewed study has helped to give perspective to the current study. The study, which was done in 1996, concluded that the image of women in Nigerian films was found to be very bad and capable of negatively influencing the perception of women among the large audience of video films in Nigeria. Eighteen years on, the current study uses content analysis to examine if women are still portrayed in Nollywood films.

2.2.3 Ateya, A. M. (2012). *Women empowerment as portrayed through the Egyptian cinema: Content analysis of films produced between 2001 and 2011*. M.Sc Thesis Submitted to the Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, the American University in Cairo.

Unlike the two previous studies reviewed, this study was carried out outside Nigeria. The study shares similar design, content categories and some objectives with the current study. This research analyzed the portrayal of women empowerment in the Egyptian cinema between the years 2001-2011. This specific period was chosen as this is when the Egyptian cinema started to tackle women's issues in line with real-life improvements in Egyptian women's status quo; such as the issue of Khul law, the establishment of the National Council for Women and the right to pass on the Egyptian nationality to their children to the researcher conducted a content analysis of 20 movies that were produced during the time span covered in the study and that have discussed woman's question or have presented women through different frames. The researcher explored differences in women portrayals with regard to women empowerment as compared to previous studies' findings that were conducted on movies produced in the nineties in order to trace changes that might have taken place. It is this objective that makes this research parallel to the study at hand. In this study being reviewed, the researcher focused on the Egyptian cinema

and studied movies that discussed women's issues or the woman's question produced during the 21st Century. Theoretically, the study was anchored on the concept of framing and Freire's theory of empowerment.

The study applied both quantitative and qualitative approaches in order to investigate the problem under study. In-depth interviews with cinema experts, scholars and practitioners was conducted for the qualitative data collection part, and a content analysis of movies produced during the period 2001-2011 was carried out for the quantitative data collection part. Using both approaches will help in achieving triangulation of data which could be useful in validating the research results. In-depth interviews with cinema experts, scholars and practitioners will be conducted in order to supplement the content analysis in the data collection part of this research and will help in filling some information gap. This research will use a purposive sampling.

A list of 52 female characters were coded in order to explore the different empowerment/disempowerment frames women get presented through in the Egyptian cinema as well as to gauge any differences in women portrayals than those concluded in previous studies. Also, the researcher aimed to analyze depictions of single, divorced and widowed women and whether the presence of female filmmakers in movies' production teams will affect representations of women empowerment.

The findings of this study revealed that portrayals of women have improved as compared to previous studies of movies that were produced in the nineties. Meanwhile, portrayals of women's background, age and relationship status have remained negative. Furthermore, single, divorced and widowed women were stereotyped in the Egyptian cinema. Female and male filmmakers of the movies studied in this research had similar representations of women empowerment.

In addition, findings with regard to the socio-cultural dimension of women empowerment in the public sphere also revealed that women were depicted as empowered in some elements as well as disempowered in others. Results supported that single, divorced and widowed women are depicted as disempowered with regard to socio-cultural, familial/interpersonal and psychological public spheres. In other words, they were disempowered when it comes to the society's perceptions and stereotyping, but they are less disempowered in the private sphere.

This finding resonates with findings in previous studies that articulated that single, divorced and widowed women were negatively portrayed on screen.

Finally, movies produced in the 21st Century tackled issues of great importance to the woman's question such as female autonomy, female sexuality issues and female independency. Females were also depicted through new empowerment frames as well as disempowerment ones.

Having successfully used content analysis to examine portrayals of women in Egyptian films, the current study used similar design and code sheet and adopted some of the content categories used in the reviewed study.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Severin and Tankard (2001) in Ateya (2012) proposes that theory fosters a better understanding of how the world around us works. One of the key objectives of mass communication theories is to study the effects of media consumption, and predict consequences or show relationship between variables. This section underscores the two theories that explain the thesis from a scientific point of view.

2.3.1 Feminist Muted Group Theory

Shirley and Ardener (1968) introduced the feminist muted group theory, which explains why certain groups in society are muted, silent or not heard. They suggest that in every society a social hierarchy exists, that privileges some group over others. These groups that function at the top (men) of the social hierarchy determine to a great extent the communication system of the entire society and the "mutedness" occurs because of the lack of power that is given to another group (women) that occupies the low end of the pole. They assert that women are the ones that usually are at the lower rung of the social hierarchy; hence, they are usually undermined and silenced.

Kramarae (1981) made the following key assumptions of the feminist muted group theory to include:

- That because men are the dominant group in the society, the women are perceived as less competent.

- That in order to become participating members in society women must transform their perceptions and models of perceiving into terms of dominant group.

That is to say, in a male dominated society, the assignment of roles in the cultural industries adversely affects women; to sustain supremacy men assign to themselves the more paying, more powerful and prestigious roles while leaving the weaker and less prestigious ones to women.

This theory explains why women could be misrepresented, stereotyped and underrepresented in films. Just as Alao (2011) said about the Nollywood industry where it was a male dominated one, the men set the agenda and framed the images. However, with the increased roles of women in the industry, the feminist muted group theory assumes that there should be improvements in the way women were muted and subjugated.

2.3.2 Sexual Objectification Theory

Sexual objectification theory assumes that there is a growing perception of women as physical objects of male sexual desire. This theory suggests that by reason of certain cultures, women's value is tied to their looks and sexual appeal to men. This leads to the reduction of people, especially women, to physical objects of sexual desire. Fredrickson and Roberts (1997), proponents of the objectification theory, explain that certain cultures socialise girls and women to internalise an observer's perspective on their own bodies. When young girls and women internalise an observer's perspective of their own bodies, they live much of their life in the third-person. In other words, females learn to be more concerned with observable body attributes rather than focusing on non-observable body attributes such as feelings and internal bodily states.

The objectification theory takes as a given that all women and girls in our society live in a culture in which their bodies are looked at, evaluated, and potentially objectified. Thus, the aim of objectification theory is to explicate how living in a social-cultural context that sexualises and dehumanises the female body can lead to specific negative affective experiences and mental health risks for women and girls.

What this theory means in essence is that the objectification of women in the cultural industries such as the mass media has become a global trend; various cultures are beginning to adopt that. The extent to which women are objectified in the media is almost always a reflection

of the way they are objectified in the real world. Therefore, with the growing concern for the objectification of women in the world, the extent to which Nollywood objectifies women in the home videos would supposedly be on the increase.

2.4 Summary of Review

Having reviewed various literatures on subjugation, objectification, gender portrayal in the media, Nollywood and history of Nollywood; and also theoretical frameworks as well as some related studies that are used to give context to this study, the researcher has observed that existing knowledge and previous researches had expressed concerns about the portrayal of gender, particularly women, in the media. The most striking finding is that women are highly underrepresented and objectified in most forms of media. Past studies on Nollywood portrayal of women have also shown the subjugation and objectification of women, but there is need to revisit how Nollywood portray women in terms of subjugation and objectification in order to ascertain to what extent that has changed in the recent past and at present.

Previous studies that were conducted on the portrayal of women in Nollywood films (see Okunna, 1996, 2002; Ogunleye, 2003; Azeez, 2008, 2010) can be used as a benchmark in order to measure against any changes that might have taken place in the way women are portrayed in Nigerian films.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The basic design adopted for this study was content analysis. In-depth interviews were also conducted. That is, a content analysis of films produced during the period 2000-2014 was carried out and in-depth interviews with identified film experts and scholars were conducted to supplement the content analysis in the data collection and they helped in filling some information gap. Using both designs helped in achieving triangulation of data which was useful in validating the research findings.

The two approaches above were successfully applied by Ateya (2012) in a content analysis of Egyptian films. Citing Wimmer and Dominick (2011), Ateya (2012) states that content analysis is considered the best approach when it comes to studying the portrayal of a certain group in any given medium. He further states that content analysis is used to study the image of certain groups. It is a method of studying and analyzing communication in a systematic, objective and quantitative manner for the purpose of measuring variable(s). In this case, the communication materials are Nollywood films. That is to say, this study did an objective, systematic and quantitative description or analysis of the contents of Nollywood films, exploring the issue of women subjugation and objectification as portrayed in Nollywood films during the time frame, 2000-2014.

3.2 Population of the Study

According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011), an important step in content analysis is to define the universe; which is to specify the boundaries of the body of content to be considered. In this study, the researcher focused on Nollywood films produced from 2000 to 2014 that have women playing leading or supporting roles. This specific time span is chosen, because this is when women began to take up serious technical and production roles in Nollywood. Another

important reason for the choice of the 15 year span is that it is important to study more portrayals in order to gauge the differences in the way women have been portrayed during these years and the changes that might have taken place.

The Nigerian Film and Video Censor's Board (www.nfvcb.gov.ng; accessed 19-02-2015) listed 15,054 films registered between 2000 and 2014. A review of the synopsis of the films by the researcher shows that 39% of the films have women playing leading or supporting roles. Thus, 39% of the 15,054 films registered between 2000 and 2014 summed up to 5870 films. That is to say, 5870 films make up the population for this study.

3.3 Sample Size

Wimmer and Dominick (2011, p. 157) point out that, in content analysis, there are times when sample size is chosen purposively by 'examining small sample of carefully selected' materials. The following 15 films (selected on the basis of the number years in the study frame; 2000 – 2014), out of the 5870 films which have women in leading and supporting roles between 2000 and 2014, were purposively selected:

1. Christ in Me (2003)
2. Ije (2010)
3. Rising Moon (2005)
4. Missing Angel (2004)
5. The Game (2010)
6. 30 Days (2006)
7. Amazing Grace (2006)
8. Letters to a Stranger (2007)
9. Through the Glass (2008)
10. The Figurine (2009)
11. The Mirror Boy (2011)
12. Phone Swap (2012)
13. Gold Diggin (2013)
14. Being Mrs Elliot (2014)
15. Outkast (2001)

List of Interviewees:

The following five interviewees were selected based on five predetermined areas of need in the study, including: the need to get the opinions of male and female academics in the fields of mass communication and/or theatre arts, getting the opinion of a film critic, getting the opinions of a male film producer as well as a female film producer.

1. GU., Department of Media and Performing Arts, Maurid Polytechnic, Mbiase, Akwa Ibom State.
2. BU., Department of Mass Communication, Maurid Polytechnic, Mbiase, Akwa Ibom State.
3. DJ., Film Producer, Owerri, Imo State.
4. IE., Film Producer and Director, Eket, Akwa Ibom State.
5. IN., film critic.

3.4 Sampling Technique

The researcher used purposive and simple random sampling techniques. The sampled films were drawn from the 5870 films produced in Nigeria and censored by the National Film and Video Censors Board between 2000 and 2014 which have women in leading and supporting roles. The 5870 films were listed and placed in 15 sample frames based on the various years of production. In each of the frames, the researcher randomly picked one film. Thus, after taking turns on the 15 sampling frames, 15 films were selected for coding.

According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011) purposive sample is a non-probability sample that “includes subjects or elements selected for specific characteristics or qualities and eliminates those who fail to meet these criteria”. Thus, the criteria for purposive sampling is including movies that only have women in leading and supporting roles during the time span year 2000-2014; since this study is interested in studying women portrayal, movies that have women in leading and supporting roles fit the study’s purpose. Moreover, to justify the use of purposive sampling, Riffe and Fretag (1997) cited in Halawa (2013) found that 68 percent of the *Journalism Quarterly*’s content analysis studies used purposive sampling.

3.5 Coding Instrument

The code sheet was used to record frequency of occurrences of various depictions of subjugations and objectification of women in the selected Nollywood films. The researcher was guided by the various content categories and units of analysis that are indicative of subjugations and objectification of women in the selected Nollywood films. The code sheet used in this study was originally designed by Ateya (2012) in a content analysis on women as portrayed through the Egyptian cinema. The researcher changed some elements in the code sheet for purposes of this study.

In-depth interviews with academics, critic and film experts were conducted in order to supplement the content analysis in the data collection part of this research and will help in filling some information gap. The in-depth interviews were conducted using an interview schedule with six questions.

3.6 Units of Analysis

Unit of analysis is defined as the smallest element of content analysis but the most important (Wimmer and Dominick, 2011). In this research, specifically speaking, the unit of analysis is the female character within the selected Nollywood movies. Having the female character within the movie as the unit of analysis helped to gauge the different subjugation and objectification frames women were depicted in the selected Nollywood films. Not all the female characters in movies were studied; only women in leading and supporting roles were coded.

3.7 Content Categories

The content categories in this study are those things that the researcher considers markers of subjugation and objectification or sexualisation which relate to the female characters in the selected Nollywood films. They include:

- i. Character traits.
- ii. Body parts.
- iii. Clothing/nudity.
- iv. Stance.

- v. Posture.
- vi. Language.

Those are the content categories that were coded in the selected Nollywood films. They are the different kinds of content the researcher investigated, and which helped in answering the research questions.

3.8 Content Variables

To facilitate measurement of the content categories, the content were examined accordingly using the following variables. They include:

- i. Character traits of women portrayed in coded movies: This is classified as weak, powerful, assertive, withdrawn, submissive, passive, self-independent, limited thinker, critical, follower, slave, active/cope with difficulties, progressive, sex object and regards herself as inferior to man.
- ii. Body parts of women emphasised in each frame of the coded movies: This is classified as breasts/chest, genitals, buttocks and lips.
- iii. Clothing/nudity: Classified as frames depicting a woman wearing slightly revealing clothing; wearing clothing that was somewhat revealing; wearing highly revealing and/or skin-tight clothing; wearing swimsuits and lingerie, that is, apparel that is not generally considered “clothing” at all; and wearing nothing at all (or only minimal clothing, such as socks and shoes but nothing else).
- iv. Stance: This means the stance in which the women were portrayed. This is classified as: stance that indicated subordination/subjugation; stance in which the character was dominant; and not shown in a subordinated position.
- v. Posture: This means the body positions that the females in those films assume which are suggestive of either subjugation or objectification. They are categorized as: sexually provocative, physically subdued and physically imposing.

- vi. Language: This means the languages that the females in those films used which are suggestive of either subjugation or objectification. They are categorized as: indecent, authoritative and contrite.

3.9 Validity of Instrument

The code sheet was, prior to coding, submitted to two film experts who critically evaluated it for content validity and certified that the instrument was capable of guiding the coding exercise.

3.10 Intercoder Reliability

To ensure reliability of the instruments, it is recommended that between 10 and 25 percent of the materials should be analyzed by independent coders (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011). Thus, 4 of the sampled films were independently coded by two undergraduate students in the department of Mass Communication, Imo State University, Owerri. Some training and explanation of the research objectives was given to the independent coders in order to enable them to code effectively and to familiarize them with the required content categories and units of analysis to code. The coefficient of the inter-coder reliability was calculated using the Holsti formula.

According to Holsti (1969) cited in Wimmer and Dominick (2011), the inter-coder reliability can be measured through the following:

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{2M}{N1 + N2} \times 100$$

Or simply stated as: $2M/N1+N2 \times 100$

Where:

M is the number of coding decisions on which two coders agreed on,

N1 is the total number of coding decisions by the first coder.

N2 is the total number of coding decisions by the second coder.

Based on the Holsti formula, reliability = $\frac{2(99)}{112 + 112} \times 100 = 88.3\%$

3.11 Method of Data Analysis

Frequencies and percentages were used at descriptive level to analyse the data collected and collated from the code sheets, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 19. The software was used to generate charts and tables. The Chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to test the hypotheses.

The responses from the interviewees were analyzed qualitatively and used to support the findings of the content analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS

This chapter presents and analyzes the data collected via content analyses of the fifteen films selected between the years 2000 and 2014 – films where women played primary/leading or supporting roles. This specific period was chosen as this was when women began to take part in the technical aspect of film production in an industry that was hitherto thought to be a male-dominated one. Data organisation and analysis were carried out using version 19 of the SPSS computer programme. This chapter also presents answers to the research questions, tests the hypotheses and discusses the various findings.

This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section presents the data coded from the films and analyzes them on the basis of the SPSS; the second section does the test of hypothesis using the Chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation; and the third section discusses the findings and answers the research questions using the quantitative and qualitative data obtained from the content analysis and the in-depth interview

4.1 Presentation of Coded Data

The researcher hereby presents the data coded from the 15 selected home videos.

Table 4.1: The Home Video Genres Identified

Movie Genre	Frequency	%
Drama	3	20
Ritual	2	13.3
Comedy	1	6.7

Fantasy/Adventure	1	6.7
Epic/Cultural	2	13.3
City Girl	2	13.3
Romance	4	26.7
Total	15	100

Following Adenugba's (2007, p. 23) genre categorization of Nigerian home videos as drama, evangelical, ritual, comedy, action, epic/cultural, city girl, romance and fantasy genres, Table 4.1 shows the different genres of the coded home videos. The following genres were identified: drama, ritual, comedy, action, epic/cultural, city girl and romance. Only the evangelical and action genres were not identified in the films coded.

As shown in Table 4.1, 3 (20%) of the 15 films coded were dramas; 2(13.3%) were rituals; 1(6.7%) was a comedy; 1(6.7%) was a fantasy film; 2(13.3%) were epic/cultural; 2(13.3%) were city girl films and 4(26.7%) were romance.

Table 4.2: Role of Female Characters within the Coded Films

Role	Frequency	%
Lead/Primary	13	26.5
Supporting	36	73.5
Total	49	100

Women coded in those films played either lead or supporting roles. Forty-nine (49) of such women were identified in the 15 selected films. As shown in Table 4.2, 13 (26.5%) of the coded females are primary or lead characters in the coded movies, whereas 36 (73.5%) are supporting characters.

Table 4.3: Gender of Makers of the Coded Home Videos

Gender	Director	Writer	Producer
Female	5 (33.3%)	6 (40%)	5 (33.3%)

Male	10 (66.7%)	9 (60%)	10 (66.7%)
Total	15 (100%)	15 (100%)	15 (100%)

Table 4.3 compares frequencies of female filmmakers to frequencies of male filmmakers. The Table demonstrates the gender of the filmmakers: the directors, the writers and the producers of the home videos.

As shown in Table 4.3, 5(33.3%) of the movies are directed by females, as compared to 10(66.7%) directed by males. 6 (40%) of the movies are written by females as compared to 9 (60%) written by males. As for the production of the home videos, 5 (33.3%) movies are produced by female producers as compared to 10 (66.7%) produced by male producers. The subtle implication of having the same data under ‘Directors’ and ‘Producers’ in Table 4.3 is that the same female directors produced their own films.

Table 4.4: Character Traits the Women Exhibited in the Selected Films

Traits Exhibited	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Weak	3	3.5	3.5	3.5
Powerful	7	8.2	8.2	11.8
Assertive	6	7.1	7.1	18.8
Withdrawn	5	5.9	5.9	24.7
Submissive	3	3.5	3.5	28.2
Passive	4	4.7	4.7	32.9
Self-Independent	9	10.6	10.6	43.5
Limited Thinker	4	4.7	4.7	48.2
Critical	6	7.1	7.1	55.3
Follower	2	2.4	2.4	57.6
Slave	3	3.5	3.5	61.2
Active	14	16.5	16.5	77.6
Cope With Difficulties	7	8.2	8.2	85.9
Progressive	8	9.4	9.4	95.3
Sex Object	2	2.4	2.4	97.6
Regards Herself As Inferior To Man	2	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Various character traits were coded for 85 times in the selected home videos as demonstrated by the 49 women coded in the films. As indicated in the Table 4.4 above, the

character traits include being weak, powerful, assertive, withdrawn, submissive, passive, self-independent, limited thinker, critical, follower, slave, active, cope with difficulties, progressive, sex object and regards herself as inferior to man.

As shown in the Table, of the 85 character traits coded as demonstrated by the women in the films, 3(3.5%) demonstrated weakness, 7(8.2%) demonstrated power, 6(7.1%) demonstrated assertiveness, 5(5.9%) were withdrawn, 5(3.5%) were submissive, 4(4.7%) were passive, 9(10.6%) were self-independent, 4(4.7%) showed limited thinking, 6(7.1%) were critical, 2(2.4%) were followers, 3(3.5%) demonstrated slavery or servitude, 14(16.5%) were active, 7(8.2%) coped with difficulty, 8(9.4%) were progressive, 2(2.4%) were at some points seen as sex objects and 2(2.4%) were situations where a woman regards herself as inferior to man.

Fig 4.1 Pareto Control Chart of Female Characters' Traits in the Home Videos

The Pareto chart in Fig 4.1 above indicated the following dominant or non-subjugate character traits jutting out mostly from the rest of the traits: active, self-dependent, progressive, cope with difficulty, critical and assertive. The subjugate traits lay on the tail end of the chart.

Table 4.5: Body Parts of Females Emphasized in the Home Videos

Body Parts	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Breasts/Chest	17	32.1	32.1	32.1
Buttocks	29	54.7	54.7	86.8
Lips	7	13.2	13.2	100.0
Genitals	0	0	0	100.0
Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Various body parts that are suggestive of sexual objectification were coded in the selected home videos as exhibited by the 49 women coded in the films. As indicated in the Table 4.5 above, the body parts include breasts/chest, genitals, buttocks and lips.

As shown in the Table, in the 15 coded home videos and from the 49 girls who played lead and supporting roles in the films, on 17 (32.%) occasions, the females' breast/chest was emphasised; on 29(54.7%) occasions, the buttocks were emphasized; and on 7(13.2%) occasions, the lips were emphasized.

Fig 4.2: Pie Chart of Body Parts of Females Emphasized in the Home Videos

The pie chart in Fig 4.2 indicates the proportion of the body parts that are suggestive of sexual objectification which were coded in the selected home videos as exhibited by the 49 women coded in the films. Most of the time, as the buttock field indicates, the buttocks (and to a great degree, the breast/chest region) are the mostly emphasized body parts that are suggestive of sexualisation.

Table 4.6 Clothing/Nudity Trends among Female Characters in the Films

Valid	Clothing Trend	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Slightly revealing	25	32.5	32.5	32.5
	Somewhat revealing	38	49.4	49.4	81.8
	Highly revealing	11	14.3	14.3	96.1
	Wearing apparel that is not generally considered “clothing”	3	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Wearing nothing at all	0	0	0	100.0

Valid	Clothing Trend	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Slightly revealing	25	32.5	32.5	32.5
	Somewhat revealing	38	49.4	49.4	81.8
	Highly revealing	11	14.3	14.3	96.1
	Wearing apparel that is not generally considered “clothing”	3	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Wearing nothing at all	0	0	0	100.0
	Total	77	100.0	100.0	

Various clothing/nudity trends were coded in the selected home videos as exhibited by the 49 women coded in the films. as indicated in the table 4.6 above, the clothing/nudity trends are categorised as: slightly revealing clothing, somewhat revealing clothing, highly revealing clothing, wearing apparel that is not generally considered “clothing” and wearing nothing at all.

As shown in the Table, in the 15 coded home videos and from the 49 girls who played lead and supporting roles in the films, on 25(32.5%) occasions, the women wore slightly revealing clothes; on 38(49.4%) occasions, the women wore somewhat revealing clothes; on 11(14.3%) occasions, the women wore highly revealing; and on 3(3.9%) occasions, the women wore apparel that is not generally considered “clothing”.

Fig 4.3: Pareto Control Chart of Clothing/Nudity Trends among Female Characters in the Films

The Pareto chart in Fig 4.3 above shows the bars of ‘somewhat revealing’ and ‘slightly revealing’ clothes overhanging above the rest of the clothing/nudity trends coded in the films.

Table 4.7 Stance portrayed by the Women in the Home Videos

Stance	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Stance that indicated subordination/subjugation	36	28.3	28.3	28.3
Stance in which the character was dominant	68	53.5	53.5	81.9
Stance not clearly determined	23	18.1	18.1	100.0
Total	127	100.0	100.0	

The stance portrayed by the women was coded in the 15 selected home videos as indicated in the table 4.7 above. The stance was indicative of the extent of their subjugation or otherwise, and the said stance was evaluated by their disposition and attitude towards things.

As shown in the Table, in the 15 coded home videos and from the 49 girls who played lead and supporting roles in the films, on 36(28.3%) occasions, the women’s stance to issues indicated subordination/subjugation; on 68(53.5%) occasions, the women’s stance was the one in which their character was dominant; and on 23(18.1%) occasions, the women’s stance was not clearly determined by the researcher.

Fig 4.4 Bar Chart of Stance portrayed by the Women in the Home Videos

The bar chart in Fig 4.4 above shows the bar at the middle in which the female character’s stance was dominant overhanging above the rest of the other stance coded in the films.

Table 4.8 Social Class of Women in the Home Videos

Social Class	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Upper	17	34.7	34.7	34.7
Upper-middle	14	28.6	28.6	63.3
Middle	11	22.4	22.4	85.7
Lower-middle	4	8.2	8.2	93.9
Lower	2	4.1	4.1	98.0
Undetermined	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	49	100.0	100.0	

The social class of the women was coded in the 15 selected home videos as indicated in the table 4.8 above. The social class of the women was categorized as upper, upper-middle, middle, lower-middle, lower and undetermined.

As shown in the Table, in the 15 coded home videos and of the 49 girls who played lead and supporting roles in the films, 17(34.7%) belonged to the upper social class; 14(28.6%) belonged to the upper-middle social class; 11(22.4%) belonged to the middle social class; 4(8.2%) belonged to the lower-middle social class; 2(4.1%) belonged to the lower social class and 1(2%) belonged to a social class that the researcher could not classify.

Fig 4.5 Pareto Control Chart of Social Class of Women in the Home Videos

The Pareto chart in Fig 4.5 above shows the bars of ‘upper and ‘middle-upper social classes overhanging above the rest of the social classes coded in the 15 selected films.

Table 4.9 Sexual Activities Engaged by Women in the Home Videos

Sexual Activities	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Intimate Touching	12	19.7	19.7	19.7
Passionate Kissing	16	26.2	26.2	45.9
Casual Touching	13	21.3	21.3	67.2
Implied Intercourse	6	9.8	9.8	77.0
Disrobing	6	9.8	9.8	86.9
Approximate Nudity	1	1.6	1.6	88.5
Sustained Romance	7	11.5	11.5	100.0
Actual intercourse	0	0	0	100.0
Total	61	100.0	100.0	

The various sexual activities engaged by the women in the 15 selected home videos were coded as indicated in the table 4.10 above. The various identified sexual activities engaged by then women intimate touching, passionate kissing, casual touching, implied intercourse, disrobing, nude and sustained romance; but there was no incidence of actual intercourse.

As shown in the Table, on 12(19.7%) occasions, some of the 49 girls who played lead and supporting roles in the selected films engaged in intimate touching; on 16(26.2%) occasions, they engaged in passionate kissing; on 13(21.3%) occasions, they engaged in casual touching; on 6(9.8%) occasions, they engaged in implied intercourse; on 6(9.8%) occasions, they engaged in disrobing; on 1(1.6%) occasion, they engaged in approximate nudity; and on 7(11.5%) occasions, they engaged in sustained romance.

Fig 4.6 Bar Chart of Sexual Activities Engaged by Women in the Home Videos

The bar chart in Fig 4.6 above shows the bars of ‘passionate kissing’ and ‘casual touching’ jutting above the rest of the other job statuses coded in the films.

Table 4.9 Initiators of the Sexual Activities in the Home Videos

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Men	53	86.9	86.9	86.9
Women	8	13.1	13.1	100.0
Total	61	100.0	100.0	

The initiators of the various sexual activities engaged by the women in the 15 selected home videos were coded as indicated in the table 4.11 above.

As shown in the Table, on 53(86.9%) occasions, the various sexual activities engaged by the women were initiated by the men; and on 8(13.1%) occasions, the various sexual activities engaged by the women were initiated by the women.

Fig 4.7 Pareto Chart of Initiators of the Sexual Activities in the Home Videos

The Pareto chart in Fig 4.7 above shows the projection of the bar for men as initiators of the sexual activities in the home videos.

Table 4.10: Sexual objectification of women in the films (2000-2014)

Year	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Valid Percentage</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
2000-2004	16	30.2	30.2	30.2
2005-2009	12	22.6	22.6	52.8
2010-2014	25	47.1	47.1	100
Total	53	100	100	

Table 4.10 shows the extent of sexual objectification of women in the selected home videos from 2000 to 2014. As shown in the table, between 2000 and 2004, there were 16(30.2%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected films; between 2005 and 2009, there were 12(22.6%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected

films; and between 2010 and 2014, there were 25(47.1%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected films.

Table 4.11: Blatant subjugation of women in the films (2000-2014)

Year	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Valid Percentage</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
2000-2004	14	41.2	41.2	41.2
2005-2009	4	11.7	11.7	52.9
2010-2014	16	47.1	47.1	100
Total	34	100	100	

Table 4.11 shows the extent of blatant subjugation of women in the selected home videos from 2000 to 2014. As shown in the table, between 2000 and 2004, there were 14(41.2%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films; between 2005 and 2009, there were 4(11.7%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films; and between 2010 and 2014, there were 16(47.1%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films.

Table 4.12: Body postures of the women in the films (2000-2014)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Sexually provocative	23	47.9	47.9	47.9
Physically subdued	9	18.8	18.8	66.7
Physically imposing	16	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	48	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.12 shows the body positions that the females assume which are suggestive of either subjugation or objectification in the selected home videos from 2000 to 2014. As shown in the table, there were 23(47.9%) incidences of sexually provocative postures in the selected films; there were 9(18.8%) incidences of physically subdued postures in the selected films; and there were 16(33.3%) incidences of physically imposing postures in the selected films.

Table 4.13: Language used by the women in the films (2000-2014)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Indecent	16	27.1	27.1	27.1
Authoritative	32	54.2	54.2	81.3
Contrite	11	18.7	18.7	100.0
Total	59	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.13 shows the languages that the females used which are suggestive of either subjugation or objectification in the selected home videos from 2000 to 2014. As shown in the table, there were 16(27.1%) instances where indecent languages were used in the selected films; there were 32(54.2%) instances where authoritative languages were used in the selected films; and there were 11(18.7%) instances where contrite languages were used in the selected films.

4.2 Test of the Hypotheses

In this section, the researcher tests the five (5) hypotheses proposed in the study, using various kinds of parametric and nonparametric tests. The various analyses were once again based on the use of SPSS computer programme Version 19. The hypotheses are tested in the null.

Here is a statement of the null hypotheses:

H_{0i}: There is no significant difference in the portrayal of subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years.

H_{0ii}: There is no significant difference in the portrayal of objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years.

H_{0iii}: There is no significant relationship between gender of producers and the extent of subjugation and objectification of women in Nollywood films.

4.2.1. Hypothesis One: *There is no significant difference in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years.*

Table 4.14: Calculations for X^2 Tests

Year	O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
2000-2004	14	11.3	2.7	7.29	0.6
2005-2009	4	11.3	-7.3	53.29	4.7
2010-2014	16	11.4	4.6	21.16	1.9
Total	34	34			7.2

$$X^2 = 7.2$$

$$df = 3 - 1 = 2 \text{ (i.e. } k - 1)$$

At 2 degrees of freedom and 0.05 margin of error, critical value = 5.991.

Chi-square calculated value, 7.2, is greater than the critical value, 5.991. From the chi-square decision rule, when calculated value is greater than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is confirmed.

As a result, the researcher confirms the alternate hypothesis that there is a significant difference in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years.

4.2.2. Hypothesis Two: *There is no significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years.*

Table 4.15: Calculations for X^2 Tests

Year	O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
2000-2005	16	17.6	-1.6	2.56	0.14
2005-2010	12	17.7	-5.7	32.49	1.8
2010-2014	25	17.7	7.3	53.29	3
Total	53	53			4.94

$$X^2 = 4.94$$

$$df = 3 - 1 = 2 \text{ (i.e. } k - 1)$$

At 2 degrees of freedom and 0.05 margin of error, critical value = 5.991.

Chi-square calculated value, 4.94, is less than the critical value, 5.991. From the chi-square decision rule, when calculated value is less than the critical value, the null hypothesis is confirmed and the alternate hypothesis is rejected.

As a result, since the chi-square calculated value, 4.94, is less than the critical value, 5.991, the researcher confirms the null hypothesis and rejects the alternate hypothesis that there is a significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years.

That is to say, there has not been any significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years.

4.2.3. Hypothesis Three: *There is no significant relationship between gender of producers and the extent of subjugation and objectification of women in Nollywood films.*

Table 4.16: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Calculations

Year	Films by women	Subjugation & Objectification (X)	X ²	Films by men	Subjugation & Objectification (Y)	Y ²	XY
2000-2005	1	13	169	3	30	900	390
2005-2010	2	30	900	2	45	2025	1350
2010-2014	2	24	576	5	38	1444	912
Total	5	67	1645	10	113	4369	2650

Using the following formula, the researcher tests the hypothesis above:

$$r = \frac{nEXY - EXEY}{\sqrt{[nEX^2 - (EX)^2] [EY^2 - (EY)^2]}}$$

Therefore:

$$r = \frac{(15)(2650) - (67)(113)}{\sqrt{(15)[(1645) - 4489][(15)(4369) - 12769]}}$$

$$r = \frac{39750 - 7571}{\sqrt{(24675 - 4489)(65535 - 12769)}}$$

$$r = \frac{32179}{\sqrt{(20186)(52766)}}$$

$$r = \frac{32179}{\sqrt{1065134476}}$$

$$r = \frac{32179}{32626.3}$$

$$r = 0.9$$

Correlation coefficient = 0.9

From the Table 4.15 below, a coefficient of 0.9 shows a strong and high correlation. In other words, there is a correlation between the gender of the person producing the films and the extent of sexual objectification and subjugation of women in Nollywood films.

Table 4.17 Classification of Correlation

Range	Interpretation
0.0 to 0.2	Very weak
0.2 to 0.4	Weak and low
0.4 to 0.7	Moderate
0.7 to 0.9	Strong and high
0.9 to 1.9	Very strong and very high

Source: Rowntree (1987) in Anyanwu (2014, p.148)

4.3 Discussion of Findings/Answering Research Questions

In this section, the researcher discussed the findings of the study by answering the research questions that guided this study, with the aid of data presented and analyzed in the foregoing segments as well as the test of hypotheses and theoretical framework.

4.3.1 Research Question 1: *To what extent are women subjugated in select Nollywood films?*

It is obvious from the interview responses and data coded from the films, that women were not significantly subjugated in the select Nollywood films. The character traits identified in the selected home videos occasions where the women were portrayed as weak, powerful, assertive, withdrawn, submissive, passive, self-independent, limited thinker, critical, follower, slave, active, cope with difficulties, progressive, and regards herself as inferior to man; but as Table 4.4 demonstrates, majority of the times, the women were portrayed as active, self-dependent, progressive; cope with difficulty, critical and assertive. As shown in Table 4.13, there were 32(54.2%) instances where authoritative languages were used in the selected films compared to other ways language was used to suggest subjugation or objectification; and there were 16(33.3%) incidences of the use of physically imposing postures in the selected films in such a way that they suggest dominance of the female characters instead of subjugation.

Data analysed in Table 4.4 shows that 3.5% demonstrated weakness, 8.2% demonstrated power, 7.1% demonstrated assertiveness, 5.9% were withdrawn, 3.5% were submissive, 4.7% were passive, 10.6% were self-independent, 4.7% showed limited thinking, 7.1% were critical, 2.4% were followers, 3.5% demonstrated slavery or servitude, 14(16.5%) were active, 7(8.2%) coped with difficulty, 9.4% were progressive, 2.4% were at some points seen as sex objects and 2.4% were situations where a woman regards herself as inferior to man.

More so, the stance of the women was indicated in the table 4.7. As shown in the Table, on 28.3% of the occasions, the women's stance to issues indicated subordination/subjugation; on 53.5% of the occasions, the women's stance was the one in which their character was dominant; and on 18.1% of the occasions, the women's stance was not clearly determined by the researcher.

That is say, for majority of the times, the women's stance was the one in which their character was dominant.

Furthermore, as shown in the Table, 34.7% of the women characters belonged to the upper social class; 28.6% belonged to the upper-middle social class; 22.4% belonged to the middle social class; 8.2% belonged to the lower-middle social class; 4.1% belonged to the lower social class and 2% belonged to a social class that the researcher could not classify. That is to say, majority of the female characters belonged to the upper-middle social class.

What the data analyses above have proven is that, while scholars like Ojiakor (1997), Okunna (2002, p. 1), Ikokwu (2002, p. 13), etc., have all noted that women's subordination and men's dominance are so pronounced in all subcultures of the Nigerian society, this can not exactly be said of Nollywood in the 21st Century. From the researcher's analysis of Nigerian films produced in the 21st Century, majority of the times, the women were portrayed as active, self-dependent, progressive; cope with difficulty, critical and assertive. The women's stance was the one in which their character was dominant, and majority of the female characters belonged to the upper-middle social class.

Mr. Nwokeocha (a film critic) said that the claim of female subjugation holds water only when the Nigerian film industry just started; when most of the themes of Nigerian films revolved around female maltreatment by in-laws, especially following her husband's death. However today, there seems to be a departure in the subjugation of woman as women now take dominant roles in the films, and are no longer as muted as they were in the early days of Nollywood. Therefore in the 21st century (between 2000 and 2014) women are not significantly subjugated in Nollywood films.

4.3.2 Research Question 2: *To what extent are women objectified in select Nollywood films?*

Analysis of the various data and interview responses demonstrate that women are highly sexually objectified in the selected home videos. Data analyzed in the Table 4.5, indicated a 32% emphasis on the females' breast/chest; 54.7% emphasis on the female's buttocks and 13.2% emphasis on the females' lips. Further analysis in Table 4.6 showed most of the times, women were portrayed as indecent dressers. 32.5% of the times where women wore sexually suggested

clothes, they wore slightly revealing clothes; 49.4% of the times, they wore somewhat revealing clothes; 14.3% of the times, they wore highly revealing; and 3.9% of the times, they wore apparel that is not generally considered “clothing”. Moreover, Table 4.12 indicated that there were 23 occasions where there were sexually provocative postures by the females in the selected films, representing 47.9% of the times in which the body positions of the females suggested either subjugation or objectification; and Table 4.13 indicated that there were 16(27.1%) instances where indecent languages were used in the selected films.

The various identified sexual activities engaged by the women in the films included intimate touching, passionate kissing, casual touching, implied intercourse, disrobing, nude and sustained romance; but there was no incidence of actual intercourse. 19.7% of the girls engaged in intimate touching; 26.2% of them engaged in passionate kissing; 21.3% of them engaged in casual touching; on 9.8% of them engaged in implied intercourse; 9.8% of them engaged in disrobing; 1.6% of them engaged in approximate nudity; and 11.5% of them engaged in sustained romance.

In the midst of these sexual representations, 86.9% of the sexual activities engaged by the women were initiated by the men; whereas only 13.1% of the sexual activities engaged by the women were initiated by the women.

What this analysis confirms is Saul’s (2003) explanation that some feminist think that women in our society are more identified and associated with their bodies than are men, and this is so. This has lent credence to the objectification theory which assumes that all women and girls in our society live in a culture in which their bodies are looked at, evaluated, and potentially objectified.

It is a situation that Ubong Boniface (lecturer of Mass Communication) calls, “an appalling situation in most films where women dance about naked, wear skimpy clothes.” In her opinion, Usen Glory (lecturer of Media and Performing Arts) understood that most Nigerian movies do not end until a girl is seen wearing provocative cloth and is portrayed as harlot or in a way a sex monger.” She noted that ‘the other day, in one of the Nigerian films, a young lady’s underwear was showing, very glaring on set. The producers of the films are also guilty. Why didn’t they edit that?’

The data and personal communication above indicate that women are sexually objectified in Nollywood films and it is a concern to women and scholars of mass communication and theatre arts that women are projected in a way that objectifies them.

4.3.3 Research Question 3: *What is the extent of change in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years?*

From the various interview and questionnaire responses, the researcher concludes that there is no departure from the objectification concerns raised about women in Nollywood films in the early studies, prior to the 21st Century. Data analyzed in Table 4.10 shows between 2000 and 2005, there were 16(30.2%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected films; between 2005 and 2010, there were 12(22.6%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected films; and between 2010 and 2014, there were 25(47.1%) incidences of objectification of the female characters in the selected films. There is no obvious improvement or difference in sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over those years.

The test of hypothesis reveals a Chi-square calculated value of 4.94, and a critical value, 5.991: an indication that there has not been any significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years. The earlier studies that formed the benchmark for comparing the improvement of objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years concluded that women were portrayed as sexual objects in Nollywood films (Azeez, 1996; Okunna, 2000, etc.), that finding still reflects present representation of women in today's Nollywood.

The finding that women are still objectified in Nollywood films is not surprising. This had been predicted by the sexual objectification theory which assumes that there is a growing perception of women as physical objects of male sexual desire. The theory says that all women and girls in our society live in a culture in which their bodies are looked at, evaluated, and potentially objectified. That is to say, we expect even more objectification of women in Nollywood films as westernization continues to gain grounds and the global culture continues to break cultural boundaries all over the world.

4.3.4 Research Question 4: *What is the extent of change in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years?*

Following responses from interviewees, content analysis of the select films and comparison with findings from already existing studies, it can be inferred that there is significant improvement in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films. Data analyzed in Table 4.11 revealed that between 2000 and 2004, there were 14(41.2%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films; between 2005 and 2009, there were 4(11.7%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films; and between 2010 and 2014, there were 16(47.1%) incidences of subjugation of the female characters in the selected films.

The fact that women were not significantly subjugated in Nollywood films (2000-2014) was further attested to by analysis in the Table 4.4 and Fig 4.1. The following dominant or non-subjugate character traits were mostly observed among the women: active (16.5%), self-dependent (10.6%), progressive (9.4%), ability to cope with difficulty (8.2%), critical (7.1%) and assertive (7.1%). The subjugate traits such as weakness 3.5%), withdrawn (5.9%), situations where a woman regards herself as inferior to man (2.4%) and showed limited thinking (4.7%). The chi-square result also confirms that there is a significant difference in the subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years.

Numerous studies conducted in the early years of Nollywood (1992-2000) concluded that Nollywood films did not only limit representations of women to passive and subordinate housewives, but also portrayed them as evil people, who are wicked, vindictive and unfaithful, wayward and of low morality, easily lured by material things, subservient to men, fit for domestic rather than professional and career roles, lazy and dependent on men, or weaker vessels, etc. All those were indicators of subjugation.

What the findings in this study imply is that there is significant improvement the subjugation of women in Nollywood films in the 21st Century, compared with what obtained in the early days of Nollywood.

4.3.5 Research Question 5: *Do Nollywood films produced by women have less portrayal of subjugation and objectification of women than otherwise?*

In-depth interviews yielded sufficient information to answer this research questions. More so the correlation analysis shows a coefficient of 0.9, which indicates a strong and high correlation between gender of producer and portal of subjugation and objectification. In other words, there is a correlation between the gender of the person producing the films and the extent of sexual objectification and subjugation of women in Nollywood films. There is less portrayal of subjugation (reduced to a very great extent) and objectification (sometimes there are still fair dose of objectification) of women in films produced by women.

Dan Jacobs (film producer) said that chances are that when women produce films, they want to tell people that it is also a woman's world. They want to show off. They want to suggest equality with men in those films. They undertake adventures that were hitherto known only to men. So it is a good thing that women go into film production in order to negative ways women have been portrayed in Nollywood.

Ime Nsim (film producer) further attested that most times, the female producers may not be able to make action films that are only know to men. The women prefer drama, fantasy, adventure, city girl, etc. The snag there is that there is no way you can produce films in those classification without infusing sex or romance. She said, "you might not necessarily suggest dominance by men. But you have to put in a little of romance. So I think most girls' films have lot of romance in it."

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Findings

Following the various analysis and interpretations in the previous chapter, here is a summary of the findings:

1. Women were not significantly subjugated in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014. The women's stance was mostly one in which their character was dominant and challenging stereotypes. For instance, 53.5% of the occasions, the women's stance was the one in which their character was dominant; and there were 54.2% instances where authoritative languages were used by the females to suggest that their character was dominant.
2. The women were mostly portrayed as active, self-dependent, progressive; able to cope with difficulty, critical and assertive; and sometimes very emotional. In the various character traits, 14(16.5%) showed that they were active; 7(8.2%) showed that they coped with difficulty; and 8(9.4%) showed that they were progressive.
3. Women are highly sexually objectified in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014. Women were portrayed in a way that viewers can make judgments about them based on their physical appearance and their sex appeal. For instance, 54.7% of their body emphasis was on their buttocks; and 47.9% of the times in which their body positions were examined, they were sexually provocative; and 86.9% of the sexual activities engaged by the women were initiated by the men.
4. There has not been any significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years. Women have always been sexually objectified in Nigerian films. The chi-square (χ^2) computation yielded a value of 4.94, which is less than the critical table value of 5.991, an indication that there has not been any significant difference in the sexual objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years.

5. There has been significant change in the way women are subjugated in Nollywood films since the industry started. The chi-square (χ^2) computation yielded a value of 7.2, which is greater than the critical table value of 5.991. That means, subjugation seems not to be a big issue in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014.
6. There is less portrayal of female subjugation and objectification in films produced by women. The difference sometimes, however, is not significant. A coefficient of 0.9 shows a strong and high correlation between gender of film producers and extent of subjugation and objectification of women in those films. In other words, there is a correlation between the gender of the person producing the films and the extent of sexual objectification and subjugation of women in Nollywood films.

5.2 Conclusion

This study revisited the objectification and subjugation of women in Nollywood films, from the turn of the 21st century to this day by content analyzing 15 films produced between 2000 and 2014. The rationale is that with greater involvements of women in Nollywood in the 21st century, there was need to gauge if the portrayal of women changed in films produced in the 21st century; and find out how the portrayal of subjugation and objectification of women changed over the years against the benchmarks of previous studies.

The findings concluded that women were not significantly subjugated in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014, but they were highly sexually objectified in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014. While women have always been sexually objectified in Nigerian films, subjugation seems no longer an issue in Nigerian films produced between 2000 and 2014.

Therefore, with greater involvements of women in Nollywood in the 21st century, particularly in terms of administration and the technical aspects of production, there is less subjugation of women in Nollywood films but there is still significant level of objectification in the films.

5.3 Recommendations

In the light of the various findings, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Film writers should understand their role in shaping gender perception in society. They should try as much as possible to avoid presenting women as sex object. They can do that by paying more attention to the action and drama genres of films, which are less likely to have a lot of sexual roles.
2. Nigerian Film and Video Censors' Board must play its part in reducing incidence of female objectification in Nigerian films, by putting Objectification (O) as a film classification element, in the same breath as Nudity, Strong Language and Violence (NSL).

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

Future researchers should try to study sexual objectification of men in Nigerian films; because in the course of the content analysis, the coders saw subtle and blatant instances of sexual objectification of men.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR FILM EXPERTS, SCHOLARS AND VIEWERS

1. Do you feel that women are mostly portrayed in a subjugated stance in Nollywood films?
2. Do you feel that women are mostly objectified in Nollywood films?
3. Are you aware of any improvement in the portrayal of subjugation of women in Nollywood films over the years?
4. Are you aware of any improvement in the portrayal of objectification of women in Nollywood films over the years?
5. Do you feel that Nollywood films produced by women have less portrayal of subjugation and objectification of women than those produced by men?
6. (*For Scholars and Experts*): Can you say the portrayal of women in Nollywood is a reflection of the way women are perceived in our culture?

CODE BOOK

APPENDIX B: CODE BOOK

1. Name of Film: -----
2. Year of Production: -----
3. Movie Genre: -----
4. Lead/Supporting Characters Name(s): -----
5. Role within film:-----
6. Director:-----, Writer:-----, Producer:-----
7. Character traits of women portrayed in the film

0. Not clear	
1. Weak	
2. Powerful	
3. Assertive	
4. Withdrawn	
5. Submissive	
6. Passive	
7. Self- Independent	
8. Limited Thinker	
9. Critical	
10. Follower	
11. Slave	
12. Active	
13. Cope With Difficulties	
14. Progressive	
15. Sex Object	

16. Regards Herself As Inferior To Man	
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8. Body parts of women emphasized

1. Breasts/Chest	
2. Genitals	
3. Buttocks	
4. Lips	

9. Clothing/nudity trend among women in the film

a. slightly revealing	
b. somewhat revealing	
c. highly revealing,	
d. wearing apparel that is not generally considered "clothing"	
e. wearing nothing at all	

10. Stance portrayed in the film

1. Stance that indicated subordination/subjugation	
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2. Stance in which the character was dominant	
3. Stance not determined	

11. Job status of women portrayed in the film

1. Status	
2. Employed/ white collar	
3. Employed/blue collar	
4. Unemployed	
5. No given profession	
6. Student	
7. Private business	
8. High Managerial Position	
9. Low Managerial Position	
10. Undetermined	

12. Nature of job status of women portrayed in coded movies:

1. High Managerial Position	
2. Low Managerial Position	
3. Non-managerial Position	
4. Unemployed	

5. Undetermined	
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13. Sexual activities engaged by women portrayed in coded movies:

Intimate Touching	
Passionate Kissing	
Casual Touching	
Implied Intercourse	
Disrobing	
Nude	
Sustained Romance	
Actual Intercourse	

14. Social class of women portrayed in the coded films

1.Upper	
2.Upper-middle	
3.Middle	
4.Lower-middle	
5.Lower	
6.Undetermined	